

Participant Information Sheet- History-Enhanced Computing and Sustainability (HECaS)

You are invited to take part in research taking place at the University of the West of England, Bristol. The research is carried out by UWE academics there is no specific funding for the research. Before you decide whether to take part, it is important for you to understand why the study is being done and what it will involve. Please read the following information carefully and if you have any queries or would like more information please contact Ian Brooks, College of Arts, Technology and Environment, University of the West of England, Bristol ian.brooks@uwe.ac.uk

Who is organising and funding the research?

The project lead is Ian Brooks with other UWE academics as co-Investigators. Ian Brooks' bio and details of his work are available at <https://people.uwe.ac.uk/Person/IanBrooks>

There is no specific funding for this research which is carried out within the usual academic roles of the team.

What is the aim of the research?

The research is evaluating a project to enrich the learning of Computing / Computer Science students by incorporating lessons from historic parallels.. Our research questions are addressing how useful and interesting students find the added historical content. To help us answer these questions we will be conducting an online survey before and after the teaching and also some semi-structured interviews. The aim of the survey and interviews will be to collect information that will be made anonymous.

The results of our study will be analysed and used to inform the content that we teach on CCT courses at UWE. The anonymised results may also be used in conference papers and peer-reviewed academic papers.

Why have I been invited to take part?

As a student, we are interested in gaining information about your perceptions of the added historical content so the survey / interview will ask you about these things.

Do I have to take part?

You do not have to take part in this research. It is up to you to decide whether or not you want to be involved. If you do decide to take part, you will be given a copy of this information sheet to keep and will be asked to sign or agree a consent form. If you do decide to take

part, you are able to withdraw from the research without giving a reason until the point at which your data is anonymised and can therefore no longer be traced back to you. This point will take place one week from the date you signed your consent form. If you want to withdraw from the study within this period, please write to Ian Brooks (ian.brooks@uwe.ac.uk). Your grades for this module will not in any way be affected by this survey, whether you participate or choose not to participate.

What will happen to me if I take part and what do I have to do?

If you agree to take part you will be asked to take part in a short online survey and potentially a short, follow-up interview. The survey will be conducted online and the interview by Ian Brooks or another of the research team members. The team are all experienced in the subject matter and are sensitive to issues it may raise. The survey will take approximately 5 minutes and the interview approximately 15 minutes. The interviews can be carried out online with MS Teams.

The subject and focus of the discussion will be around your perception of the value of the enhanced teaching. Your answers will be fully anonymised.

Your interview will be recorded on MS Teams. It and the transcript of the interview will be saved on UWE Onedrive using anonymous filenames. Your name will not be recorded in the interview file. . A unique identifier will be used to re-identify you if you choose to withdraw from the study within the period. At the point of transcription, your voice recording will be deleted. Your data will be anonymised at this point and will be analysed with interview data from other anonymised participants.

What are the benefits of taking part?

There is no specific benefit to you from participating in the research but your views will help to shape the teaching content for future computing students.

What are the possible risks of taking part?

We do not foresee or anticipate any significant risk to you in taking part in this study. If, however, you feel uncomfortable at any time you can ask for the interview to stop. The research team are experienced in conducting interviews and are sensitive to the subject area.

What will happen to your information?

All the information we receive from you will be treated in the strictest confidence.

All the information that you give will be kept confidential and anonymised at the point of transcription or questionnaire completion. The only circumstance where we may not be able to keep your information confidential is if you tell us about activities which we have a duty to report to the police or statutory authorities. Voice recordings will be destroyed securely

immediately after anonymised transcription. Your anonymised data will be analysed together with other interview and file data, and we will ensure that there is no possibility of identification or re-identification from this point.

Where will the results of the research study be published?

A UWE internal report will be written containing our research findings to inform future teaching. Anonymous and non-identifying direct quotes may be used for publication and presentation purposes.

The anonymised results may also be used in conference papers and peer-reviewed academic papers.

Who has ethically approved this research?

The project has been reviewed and approved by College Research Ethics Committee under application number FET-2122-196. Any comments, questions or complaints about the ethical conduct of this study can be addressed to the Research Ethics Committee at the University of the West of England at:

Researchethics@uwe.ac.uk

What if something goes wrong?

In the unlikely event that something goes wrong, you can contact the lead researcher Ian Brooks (ian.brooks@uwe.ac.uk) or the Research Ethics Committee (Researchethics@uwe.ac.uk).

What if I have more questions or do not understand something?

If you would like any further information about the research please contact in the first instance:

Ian Brooks, ian.brooks@uwe.ac.uk

Thank you for agreeing to take part in this study.

You will be given a copy of this Participant Information Sheet and your signed Consent Form to keep.